

ISOTHERMAL MODELS OF ADSORPTION OF IRON IONS BY ORGANOBENTONITES IN

¹Khandamova D.K., ²Nurullaev Sh.P., ³Talipova X.C.

¹Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, PhD assistant

²Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Professor

³Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506055>

Abstract. This work studied adsorption isotherms of Fe^{+2} ions in wastewater with new modified adsorbents based on Freundlich, Langmuir, Dubinin-Radishkovich, and Temkin isotherm models. Adsorbents modified with organic substances (trimethylammonium and triethylammonium bentonites) effectively adsorb iron ions from municipal wastewater. The adsorption behavior of synthesized adsorbents (TAB and TAB) was systematically studied. The adsorption of Fe^{+2} ions on the adsorbents was 0.151 mg/g in PBG bentonite, 0.164 mg/g in TMAB and 0.168 mg/g in TEAB. The adsorption isotherm and kinetic studies revealed that the data aligned well with the Langmuir isotherm, and the kinetics fit better with the pseudo-second-order model.

Keywords: adsorption, modification, wastewater, bentonite, iron ions, Freundlich, Langmuir, Dubinin-Radishkovich and Temkin isothermal models.

Introduction. The contamination of water resources with iron (Fe^{2+}) ions is a significant environmental problem due to its negative impact on human health and aquatic ecosystems. Traditional water treatment methods often fail to effectively remove Fe^{2+} ions [1]. In recent years, researchers have investigated the use of bentonite-based adsorbents as a promising method for removing Fe^{2+} . Consequently, it has been determined that utilizing activated bentonites for purifying Fe^{2+} ions in wastewater (including sewage) offers several advantages due to its unique properties [2]. Activated bentonites have a high surface area and porous structure, crucial for Fe^{2+} ion adsorption. The ion-exchange properties of bentonites effectively contribute to the purification of wastewater from Fe^{2+} ions. In this process, the degree of adsorption depends on various factors such as the concentration of Fe^{2+} ions, water chemistry, operational costs, and specific program requirements [3]. Currently, modern methods for treating polluted water include chemical precipitation, photocatalysis, flotation, ion exchange, electrochemical treatment, adsorption, coagulation, flocculation, and membrane technologies [4].

Research methods. The object of the study is Navbakhor bentonite (PBG brand), which is considered a local raw material, modified with organic substances such as trimethylammonium (TMAB) and triethylammonium (TEAB), and the adsorption properties of iron ions in aqueous solutions were studied.

The adsorption of Fe^{2+} ions in aqueous solutions of adsorbents was calculated using the following equation:

$$Q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \cdot V}{W} \quad (1)$$

where: C_0 is the initial concentration of Fe^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions in solution (mg/L); C_e - equilibrium concentration of Fe^{2+} ions in adsorption (mg/L); W - mass of adsorbents, expressed in grams (g), V - volume of Fe^{2+} solution, expressed in liters.

The percentage of adsorbates (Fe^{2+}) absorbed by the adsorbents (%) was calculated quantitatively according to equation (2) [5].

$$(\%) = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \cdot V}{W} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

The data obtained from experiments on the adsorption of Fe^{2+} ions on bentonites in water were analyzed using the Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, and Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm models. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm model is described by equation (3):

$$q_e = \frac{q_m K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (3)$$

Here: q_m is the maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g), K_L is the Langmuir constant (mg⁻¹).

The Freundlich equation is an empirical model of adsorption on a heterogeneous surface, which can be represented by the following equation (4):

$$q_e = K_F + C_e^{1/n} \quad (4)$$

Here: K_F -Freindlich constant (mg/g), n -adsorption intensity.

The isothermal model of Temkin is described by the equation $q_e = B \ln(A_T C_e)$ (5).

where: the B_T - Temkin constant; The equilibrium adsorption constant of A_T - Temkin (L/g); B_T is the heat of adsorption (J/mol).

The Dubinin-Radishkovich model equation is expressed as follows:

$$q_e = q_{max} \exp^{-K_D - R \varepsilon^2} \quad (6)$$

Here: q_{max} - high adsorption capacity of adsorbents (mg/g); K_{D-R} is the Dubinin-Radushkevich constant (mol²/kJ²); ε is the energy potential of Polanyi.

Analysis of the obtained results. Adsorbents were weighed on analytical scales in an amount of 5 grams, placed in a solution prepared in the presence of 500 ml of iron sulfate at various concentrations, mixed, settled for 1 hour, and filtered. The total iron concentration was determined by the spectrophotometric method. The essence of the method lies in the fact that iron (III) oxide is quickly reduced to iron (II) oxide in an alkaline environment. This determines the total amount of iron (II) and iron (III) ions ($\lambda=420$ nm) in an alkaline medium. [6]. The adsorption isotherms of iron ions in solution using synthesized adsorbents were studied using the Freundlich, Langmuyer, Dubinin-Radishkovich, and Temkin isotherm models. Using these models, the adsorption data was analyzed and the main parameters of the adsorption process were determined (Fig. 1). According to the obtained results, the adsorption of Fe^{+2} ions on the adsorbents was 0,111 mg/g in PBG bentonite, 0,164 mg/g in TMAB and 0,198 mg/g in TEAB, respectively.

A sharp increase in the adsorption capacity of adsorbents was observed due to an increase in the amount of adsorbent concentration in aqueous solutions. However, it should be noted that strong interactions between adsorbate molecules weaken the interaction of the ion with the adsorbent, resulting in adsorption isotherms often coinciding with a critical point. In such cases, the accumulation of adsorbed molecules on the surface of the adsorbent (located in the form of clusters, etc.) is explained by the multifunctional nature of the adsorbate and the strong adsorption of the solvent. In some cases, the solvent can displace the adsorbate molecules.

Analysis using the Freundlich model. The Freundlich equation, or Freundlich adsorption isotherm, is an adsorption isotherm that represents the empirical relationship between the amount of gas adsorbed on a solid surface and the gas pressure. The same relationship holds for the concentration of solute adsorbed on the surface of a solid and for the concentration of solute in the liquid phase. In 1909, Herbert Freundlich gave an expression describing the isothermal change in the adsorption of the amount of adsorbed gas per unit mass of a solid adsorbent with gas pressure

[7] . The results of adsorption of Fe^{+2} ions on modified adsorbents using the Freundlich model are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Isotherms of adsorption of iron ions on adsorbents at 303K.

Figure 2. Isotherms of adsorption of iron ions on adsorbents at a temperature of 303°C according to the Freundlich model.

The Freundlich isotherm model indicates good adsorption at $0 < 1/n < 1$. In this case, the degree of adsorption decreases with increasing concentration. The values of $1/n$ in PBG, TMAB, and TEAB adsorbents are 0.836, 0.789, and 0.65, respectively, and the values of n are greater than

1 (PBG = 1.19, TMAB = 1.53, TEAB = 1.26). When $n > 1$, it means that adsorption is strong, in this case, adsorption efficiency decreases with increasing concentration. The parameters of the Freundlich model isotherms are given in Table 1.

Analysis using the Langmuir model. Langmuir's adsorption model explains adsorption by assuming that the adsorbate behaves as an ideal gas under isothermal conditions. According to the model, adsorption and desorption are reversible processes. In 1916, Irving Langmuir presented his own model for the adsorption of species on simple surfaces. Langmuir was awarded the Nobel Prize for his work in surface chemistry in 1932. He hypothesized that there were a certain number of equivalent sites on a given surface to which the species could "adhere" through physisorption or chemisorption. His theory began when he put forward the idea that gaseous molecules do not return from the surface elastically, but are held up similarly to the groups of molecules in solids [8,9]. The Langmuir isotherm model describes the main characteristics of adsorption isotherms, namely monolayer adsorption and the proximity of the adsorbent to the adsorbate [10]. The experimental results obtained using the Langmuir model of Fe^{+2} ion adsorption on adsorbents are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Adsorption isotherms of iron ion adsorption on adsorbents using the Langmuir model at 303°C.

The correlation coefficients (R^2) according to the Langmuir model were 0,921 for PBG, 0,964 for TMAB, and 0,947 for TEAB. In the Langmuir model, $R(L)$ (or separation coefficient, separation factor) is an important parameter representing the ease of adsorption. It describes how adsorption occurs depending on the initial adsorbate concentration according to the adsorption isotherms. The value of $R(L)$ is interpreted as follows: $R(L) > 1$: The adsorption process is unfavorable, $R(L) = 1$: The adsorption process is linear (ideal state), $0 < R(L) < 1$: The adsorption process is favorable, which indicates good adsorption, $R(L) = 0$: The adsorption process is irreversibly strong [11]. The study found that the isotherm of the Langmuir model has a separation coefficient ($R(L)$) of 0.26, 0.197, and 0.104, respectively. Therefore, the results of this adsorption

correspond to the Langmuir model. The presence of R (L) at these values indicates the efficiency and convenience of adsorption. The results of the Langmuir model isotherm are presented in Table 1.

Analysis using the Dubinin-Radushkevich model. The Dubinin-Radushkevich model is often used to estimate characteristic porosity and the visible free energy of adsorption [12]. The Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) adsorption isotherm model is based on the potential theory of adsorption developed by Polanyi [13]. Due to its basic thermodynamic basis, it is fundamentally strong and highly valued compared to other isothermal models [14]. In the Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model, the E value is stated to fall within the energy range of 8-16 kJ/mol for ion exchange adsorption [15]. The results obtained using the Dubinin-Radushkevich model of Fe^{+2} ion adsorption on modified adsorbents are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Isotherms of adsorption of iron ions on adsorbents at a temperature of 303°C according to the Dubinin-Radushkevich model.

The values of the constants are determined by the intersection of the linear model ($q_{max} = \exp(\text{intercept})$) and the slope of the tangent of the angle ($K_{D-R} = -\text{slope}$). In the literature, the value of E is emphasized as a criterion for evaluating the type of adsorption process. If the value of E is greater than 16 kJ/mol, the adsorption is chemisorption. If the value of E is less than 8 kJ/mol, it corresponds to a physical adsorption process. If it falls within the range of 8-16 kJ/mol, it indicates that ion exchange adsorption is occurring [16]. The values of the Dubinin-Radushkevich model constants for Fe^{+2} ion adsorption isotherms on PBG, TMAB and TEAB are presented in Table 1.

Analysis using the Temkin model. The Temkin isotherm model considers the influence of the indirect adsorbate-adsorbent interaction on the adsorption process. It is based on the assumption that the heat of adsorption of all molecules in the layer decreases linearly due to an increase in the surface coverage of the adsorbent. The decrease in the heat of adsorption is linear, not logarithmic, as in the Freundlich isotherm. Furthermore, adsorption is characterized by a uniform distribution of binding energy up to the maximum binding energy [17]. To determine the correspondence of the obtained isotherms to the Temkin isotherm, a graph of the dependence q_e

and $\ln(C_e)$ was constructed. The values of B and K_T were calculated from the slope and intersection of the drawing. Figure 5 shows a diagram of Fe^{+2} adsorption on adsorbents using the Temkin model.

Figure 5. Isotherms of adsorption of iron ions on adsorbents at a temperature of 303°C according to the Temkin model.

According to the results, the correlation coefficient for this isotherm was 0.989 for TMAB. The adsorption isotherms of Fe^{+2} ions on PBG, TMAB and TEAB adsorbents are presented in the table below.

Table 1. Indicators of Fe^{2+} ion adsorption on adsorbents based on Freundlich, Langmuir, Dubinin-Radushkevich, and Temkin isotherm models.

Adsorbition Isotherm Models	Parameters	Adsorbents		
		PBG	TMAB	TEAB
Lengmyur	q_{max} (mg/g)	0.206	0.235	0.239
	K_L (L/mg)	0.056	0.081	0.171
	R_L	0.261	0.197	0.104
	R^2	0.997	0.998	0.999
Freyndlix	K_F (1/mg)	0,163	0.191	0.229
	1/n	0,836	0.789	0.650
	n	1,196	1.267	1.538
	R^2	0.917	0.964	0.947
Temkin	B_T (J/mol)	13.354	19.541	26.052
	K_T (L/mg)	0.055	0.056	0.063
	R^2	0.969	0.989	0.961
Dubinin-Radushkevich	q_m (mg/g)	4.362	4.636	5.214
	β_d (mol ² /kJ ²)	$1.23 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.86 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	E (kj/mol)	34.4	56.9	65.4
	R^2	0.834	0.881	0.865

Based on the conducted research, the correlation coefficients in the Langmuir model were more accurately described than in the Freundlich, Temkin, and Dubinin-Radiushkevich models.

According to Langmuir's model, the adsorption capacity (q_{\max}) of adsorbents in PBG is 0.206; 0.235 - in TMAB; 0.239 mg/g - in TEAB.

Conclusion. Based on the conducted studies, the Langmuir model provided a more accurate description of Fe^{2+} ion adsorption compared to the Freundlich, Temkin, and Dubinin-Radushkevich models. The adsorption capacities (q_{\max}) of the synthesized adsorbents were determined to be 0.206 mg/g for PBG, 0.235 mg/g for TMAB, and 0.239 mg/g for TEAB. Fe^{2+} ion adsorption values were found to be 0.151 mg/g for PBG, 0.164 mg/g for TMAB, and 0.168 mg/g for TEAB.

These results indicate that TEAB exhibits the highest adsorption efficiency. Additionally, adsorption efficiency depends on the adsorbent type and its adsorption capacity. The findings highlight the potential of bentonite-based adsorbents like TMAB and TEAB for effective Fe^{2+} ion removal, making them promising materials for environmental protection applications.

REFERENCES

1. Gouider, M., Feki, M., & Majdoub, H. (2018). Iron contamination in drinking water and its treatment methods. *Environmental Technology*, 40(13), 1645–1657.
2. Drosos, M., et al. (2021). "Phosphate and Ammonium Removal from Wastewaters Using Natural-Based Innovative Bentonites." *Molecules*, 26(21), 6684.
3. Kurniawan, T. A., et al. (2020). "Bentonite-Based Composites for Wastewater Treatment." *Journal of Environmental Management*, 261, 110234.
4. Tawfik A. Saleh , Mujahid Mustaqeem, Mazen Khaled ° Water treatment technologies in removing heavy metal ions from wastewater: A review. *Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring & Management* Volume 17, May 2022, 100617 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enmm.2021.100617>
5. Folahan A. Adekola1 Ismaila A. Oba1Biosorption of formic and acetic acids from aqueous solution using activated carbon from shea butter seed shells *Appl Water Sci* DOI 10.1007/s13201-016-04913
6. Mazumdar, A., & Mazumdar, P. (2021). "Determination of Total Iron Content in Water Using UV-Vis Spectroscopy." *Journal of Environmental Chemical Analysis*, 43(2), 112-118.
7. Nidheesh, P. V., & Gandhimathi, R. (2012). Electrocoagulation process for the treatment of textile wastewater containing Fe^{2+} . *Separation and Purification Technology*, 98, 57-64.
8. Joel Brian Njewa, Timothy Tiwonge Biswick, Ephraim Vunain, Cheruiyot Silas Lagat, and Solomon Omwoma Lugasi. Synthesis and Characterization of Activated Carbon from Agrowastes for the Removal of Acetic Acid from an Aqueous Solution. *Adsorption Science & Technology* Volume 2022, Article ID 7701128, 13 pages <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7701128>
9. Li, Y., & Du, Q. (2007). *Adsorption of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions by modified bentonite.* *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 143(1-2), 29-35.
10. Sari, A., Tuzen, M., & Uluozlu, O. D. (2007). *Biosorption of Pb(II) and Cd(II) from aqueous solution by macrofungus (Lentinussajor-caju) biomass: Equilibrium, kinetic and thermodynamic studies.* *Bioresource Technology*, 99(6), 1554-1560.
11. Dinis, A., et al. (2020). "Application of Langmuir Adsorption Model for Removal of Heavy Metals." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 185(8), 452-465.

12. Jaroniec, M., & Madey, R. (1989). "The use of the Dubinin-Radushkevich model in the analysis of adsorption data." *Surface Science Reports*, 10(3), 1-36.
13. Dim P. E., Mustapha L. S., Termtanun M., Okafor J. O. Adsorbtion of chromium(+2) and iron (+2) ions onto acid-modified kaolinite: Izotherm, kinetics and thermodynamics studiyes. *Arabian journal of Chemistry* (2021) 14,103064/2021. 158-165.
14. Vreebug J., "Discolouration in Drinking WaterSystems: a Particular Approach," The Netherlands:Delft Cluster, 2007.
15. B. Travalia and S. Forte, "New proposal in a biorefinery context: recovery of acetic and formic acids by adsorption onhydrotalcites," *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Data*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 4503–4511, 2020.
16. Ö. Özcan, I. Inci, and Y. S. Aşçi, "Multiwall carbon nanotube for adsorption of acetic acid," *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Data*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 583–587, 2013.
17. Zhu, H., Jia, Y., Wu, X., & Wang, H. (2009). Removal of ferrous iron from groundwater by oxidation and coagulation. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 162(2–3), 1109–1115.